

THE IMPORTANT IMPORTANCE OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND SPORTS IN EXTRACURRICULAR TIMES IN YOUNG PEOPLE

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Annotation: This article analyzes the necessity and social importance of an innovative approach to the development of physical culture. Developing a healthy lifestyle among young people is also one of the important tasks. The young generation is very susceptible to various influences. During this period, the conscious personal activity necessary for the formation of a healthy lifestyle is perfected.

Keywords: physical culture, innovation, modern approach, physical education, sports, sports pedagogy.

Introduction: In 2017-2021, the paragraph on improving the state policy on youth of the strategy of action for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan provides for the education of harmonically developed individuals who are physically healthy, mentally and mentally developed, independent-minded, loyal to the motherland, with a strictly vital point of view. "The next day of our planet, the well-being is related to how our children grow up as human beings. Our main task is to create the necessary conditions for youth to show their potential" [1].

Sports activities are considered one of the most effective forms of behavior prevention, contrary to the legal and moral norms adopted in society. It meets the capabilities of young people and attracts attention with its sensuality, creating favorable conditions for the individual to test his powers and, feeling his own, to manifest himself to others. Also, sports activities are necessary in the formation of public relations, after all, adolescents very quickly enter a certain community, perceive the activities in it as extremely important for themselves and their teams. Here it is a great educational aspect to put their mafaats next to the interests of the community. At the same time, the public in young people forms such qualities as not to challenge the legal and moral criteria adopted in the his society, to respect and appreciate their community, their territory, people, homeland, to avoid risks, to lead to victory peaks.

After all, "deciding a healthy lifestyle in society, further popularizing physical education and sports is an urgent task. We attach great importance to the rapid development of sports, the promotion and support of athletes who have achieved high results in international competitions" [2]. Therefore, within the framework of comprehensive work on the development of physical education and sports in our country, scientific research on the research of the process of growth of the physical culture of members of society is also considered important.

Already, "as we clearly define our plans and programs for the next year, we will pay special attention to the development of the most important and priority areas, further strengthening our achievements in the years of independence." Over the past years, a number of works have been carried out in our Republic, in addition, in all regions, cities and districts,

creating conditions for youth to engage in sports more widely, creating a healthy environment in society through physical education and wellness work.

Research methodology: In the development of student-youth physical culture, growing up as a harmonious personality in every possible way, there is a need to educate on the basis of a new approach to promoting physical culture, physical education, wellness, physical maturation, physical development, health promotion, a healthy lifestyle. This research work, carried out within the framework of the scientific justification of this necessity, also serves as a scientific and theoretical source of improvement of Physical Culture in young people in the pedagogical process. Also, " in the conditions of increased global competition in all aspects of development in the world, the need arises to improve the quality of human capital today before one country. It requires a radical revision of approaches to the issues of constant care about the health of the nation – the preservation of a healthy worldview of the population of all ages, physical, spiritual and intellectual health, the strengthening of physical health" [3]. "And to bring up a physically healthy and competent generation along this path is our priority, and to mobilize all our strength and resources for this."

Like other forms of Culture, physical culture is part of a system of complex personality development. Teaching students studying in higher education institutions to take care of their health, the formation of a healthy lifestyle in them through sports is the main task of Education.

From the need to clarify the concept of physical culture itself, the definitions given by specialists to this concept were studied. The concept of Physical Culture has been variously defined by experts. In particular, professor L.P. According to Matveyev, "physical culture is the achievement of the members of society in creating special tools, methods and conditions for the purposeful implementation of physical maturation and their rational use. Physical culture is a component of general culture, its rise, the basis of the development of society" [4]. Therefore, physical culture consists in the totality of the achievement of the result in terms of creating conditions for the physical development and harmonization of a person and their rational use.

Also, the development of a healthy lifestyle in young people is one of the important tasks. "The younger generation will be extremely susceptible to various influences. During this period, conscious personal activity is perfected, which is necessary for the formation of a healthy lifestyle. The development and implementation of a number of measures aimed at promoting, developing a healthy lifestyle among the population, strengthening the health of the population and prolonging human life, preventing infectious and other diseases, harmful habits, physical activity, proper nutrition and work, timely rest, as well as compliance with hygienic skills are of great importance in the life of various groups of the population, Therefore, there is an increasing need to pay special attention to the issues of the formation of a healthy lifestyle in society through the development of Physical Culture in student-youth.

Analyzes and results: Raising a healthy and harmonious generation in our country is one of the priority areas of state policy, protecting the gene pool of the nation, shaping a healthy lifestyle in the family, society, ensuring physical and spiritual perfection of the younger generation, developing love for sports, creating a material technical base of children's sports in places, building a network of modern children's sports complexes in, works on the development of children's sports, the establishment of modern sports wellness facilities not

only in the centers, but also in the most remote areas, special care and attention to boys and girls with disabilities take their place. All reforms carried out in our country are primarily evidence of the fact that they serve to ensure human interests.

The role of physical rehabilitation activities is also considered high in the development of student-youth as a mature cadre and a strong specialist. Because a healthy body will have intellectual abilities and potential. "The main indicator of the development of Physical Culture in society is the level of human health and physical formation, how important physical culture occupies in the educational and educational, production and household spheres, in the process of proper organization of leisure" [5]. Therefore, first of all, it is necessary to form a physical culture along with strong education and training of students as competitive personnel who meet world standards.

As we noted above, one of the first stages of the formation of Physical Culture in the younger generation is preschool and school physical education. Through the system of continuing education, the goal is to educate and develop the qualities of Physical Culture in the younger generation from a young age. It also brings to the surface the initial physical education in the student-youth. In the pedagogical process, young people are given the opportunity to create a conscious choice situation so that they can become athletes in the future. With this, the opportunity arises to create the basis of the physical potential necessary to become a comprehensively mature person, a perfect person.

When researching the development of Physical Culture in students, it is advisable to study the content and essence, categorical analysis of the concepts of physical maturation, physical training and physical education inherent in this category.

Physical maturation is characterized by complete health, a long period of active life of a person and several other indicators - a comprehensive high level of manifestation of the ability to work physically and mentally in any external environment, the harmonious development of physical and volitional qualities, large-scale movement skills and body shape.[6]

Now studying scientific heritage, socio-political activities and acquaintance youth charity of our above-stated ancestors is considered one of the main urgent objectives of the modern intellectuals.

Conclusion the control over the direct implementation of the highlighted measures in all regions of our country is one of the important factors in determining the development of our country, which is building a new society today. Today, in the development of the physical culture of students and young people, growing up as a comprehensively competent person, there is a need to educate on the basis of a new approach to promoting physical culture, physical education, physical maturation, physical development, health, a healthy lifestyle. Physical culture, like other forms of culture, is part of the complex developmental system of the individual. The main goal of the pedagogical process is to teach students of higher educational institutions to take care of their health, to create a healthy lifestyle in them through sports, to form skills to independently engage in physical education.

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